

SOME INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING NOUNS TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation: this article aims to highlight some effective methods of teaching nouns to young learners by the help of some games. The article lists the methods of teaching are interactive that aim to make learning process easier and more beneficial.

Key words: nouns, interactive methods, traditional methods, concept, interactive approach

Аннотация: эта статья имеет цель осветить некоторые эффективные методы обучения существительных младших школьников с помощью некоторых игр. В статье перечислены интерактивные методы обучения, которые направлены на то, чтобы сделать процесс обучения более легким и полезным.

Ключевые слова: существительные, интерактивные методы, традиционные методы, концепт, интерактивный подход.

Teaching grammar at early age and make learners use it properly requires time and efforts. To make this challenging process easier and more effectively lie on teachers' shoulders. Firstly, teachers themselves should comprehend the concept of grammatical patterns well and find some solutions to teaching problems with researching some teaching techniques and methods. In this article we would like to look briefly at some of them and highlight and point several teaching methods of

nouns and we will focus mostly on the concept of nouns and discuss the methods of teaching them to young learners.

Teaching methods are the wider techniques used to help students (pupil) achieve learning benefits, while activities are the various ways of implementing these methods.

As a fundamental part of speech, teaching nouns is an essential aspect of early childhood education. Children need to understand the concept of nouns and know how to identify them to succeed in language learning. However, teaching nouns can be challenging since it requires a fun and interactive approach to hold the attention of young learners.

1. *Noun Bingo*. This game is perfect for young learners who are just starting to grasp the concept of nouns. To play, create bingo cards with pictures and words of different nouns such as animals, fruits, and objects. Call out the words, and players have to identify the pictures on their cards until they get a bingo.
2. *Noun I Spy*. This classic game can also be adapted to teach nouns. Choose a noun, and then give clues to help children guess the noun. For example, "I spy something red and has four legs." The child who correctly guesses the noun can then be the one to give the next clue.
3. *Noun scavenger hunt*. This interactive method involves hiding pictures of different nouns around the classroom and asking students to find and label them. For example, hide a picture of a dog and ask students to find it, then label it as "dog." You can also provide hints to help children identify the nouns.
4. *Noun charades*. This game is perfect for practicing actions associated with nouns. Choose a noun and act out an associated action. For example, "cow" could be acted out using "mooing." Children have to guess the noun and then act out the associated action.
5. *Noun stories*. This method involves creating stories that use many different nouns. Have children listen to the story and try to identify all the nouns. You can also use pictures to help children visualize the story and identify the nouns.

6. *Noun categorization.* This involves sorting different types of nouns into categories. For example, sorting fruits into different types of fruits, objects into different types of objects, and animals into different types of animals. This method can be done using pictures or actual objects.

Traditional teaching methods. An evaluation in the pre-technology education context, the teacher is the sender or the course, the educational material is the information or message, and the student is the receiver of the information.

In terms of the delivery medium, the educator can deliver the message via the 'chalk-and-talk' method and overhead projector (OHP) transparencies. The directed instruction model has its foundations embedded in the behavioral learning perspective and it is a popular technique, which has been used for decades as an educational strategy in all institutions of learning.

Basically, the teacher controls the instructional process, the content is delivered to the entire class and the teacher tends to emphasize factual knowledge.

Interactive teaching methods. Interactive teaching method is that students show active involvement in the learning process. To absorb the maximum amount of information and knowledge from their teachers. Nowadays teachers use different ways to attract student's attention in Interactive teaching methods. Teachers are responsible to encourage the students to participate actively in classroom activity, apply their brains, and motivate themselves to think to have long-term memory retention. Interactive method helps to improve student's knowledge, along with their sense of interest, strength, team spirit and freedom of expression will aid raise. There are some interactive games in teaching methods. For example, teachers utilize activities which are fishbowl, brainstorming and find odd word out.

The find odd word out is more suitable to teach nouns. For instance, give some nouns and one word which is related to other parts of speech, such as verb or adjective: *book, pen, pencil, ugly*;

In conclusion, using interactive methods to teach nouns is essential to ensuring young learners grasp the concept of nouns. These interactive methods not only

make learning fun but also help children retain information better. Therefore, educators should aim to incorporate games, stories, and other interactive methods when teaching nouns to young learners.

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